

Development of Cooperative Operating Practices for Upper-Class E Traffic Management (ETM):

Human-in-the-loop Simulation Evaluation of Operational Intent Sharing and Strategic Conflict Negotiation with Industry Partners

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Abstract—The aviation industry is expanding operations into higher airspace that has been traditionally used by scientific and military vehicles. In the U.S., increasing utilization of the Upper Class E (UCE) airspace, defined to be at or above 60,000 feet, necessitates a paradigm shift in Air Traffic Management (ATM) to accommodate the diverse range of vehicles and missions, including Uncrewed Aircraft Systems (UAS), High-Altitude Platform Stations (HAPSs), and very-high speed aircraft, such as supersonics and hypersonics. To address these challenges, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) have collaborated on the development of Upper Class E Traffic Management (ETM), which promotes a community-based, cooperative approach, where operators are responsible for coordinating and managing their own operations with the Cooperative Operating Practices (COPs), established by the industry community and under the regulatory / operational authority of the FAA. The ETM concept has been developed over the years with a series of workshops and focused studies, culminating in a demonstration of ETM operations at NASA in a simulated environment, with active participation from the industry partners. The partners successfully connected their ETM Client software to the NASA’s ETM Service Supplier (ESS) by submitting and updating their Operational Intent (OIs) and their positions from remote locations and modifying their intents in response to strategic conflicts caused by overlapping operational intent (OI) volumes with another vehicle. A series of scenarios were presented to the industry partners as a step-by-step sequence of operational procedures, decision points, and necessary operator actions for the submission of their OIs and strategic conflict negotiation strategies. Associated COPs were presented, discussed, and refined based on their feedback. The partners were actively engaged throughout the process and provided valuable feedback on the OI submission and negotiation processes. Visualizing operations and role playing these processes from the operator’s perspective allowed them to provide detailed feedback and brainstorm potential improvements to operational procedures and COPs.

Keywords—Higher Airspace Operations; Upper Class E Traffic Management; Cooperative Operating Practices; High-Altitude Platform Stations; Strategic Conflict Negotiation

I. INTRODUCTION

The aviation industry is experiencing a transformation as advanced technologies like High-Altitude Long-Endurance (HALE) vehicles and stratospheric platforms emerge, expanding operations into higher airspace that has been traditionally used by scientific and military vehicles [1, 2].

In Europe, growing interest in the commercial use of space and introduction of new HALE vehicles creates a need for safe and efficient higher airspace operations (HAO) [2, 3]. The European HAO concept embeds the operations of the new vehicles within the existing Air Traffic Management (ATM) framework by allowing individual vehicles to fly according to their flight trajectories or within “4D operating zones” for vehicles with highly uncertain flight paths [4].

In the U.S., Upper Class E (UCE) airspace, defined to be at or above 60,000 feet, is expected to be occupied by the increasing utilization of HALE and stratospheric platforms, which necessitates a paradigm shift in Air Traffic Management (ATM) to accommodate the diverse range of vehicles and missions, including Uncrewed Aircraft Systems (UAS), High-Altitude Platform Stations (HAPSs), and very-high speed aircraft, such as supersonics and hypersonics [5].

The current ground-based ATC system faces limitations in managing higher airspace operations due to the constraints of ground-based radar and communication systems. To address these challenges, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) have collaborated on the development of an innovative approach to airspace management, known as Upper Class E Traffic Management (ETM) [1]. Inspired by the concept of UAS Traffic Management (UTM), ETM promotes a community-based, cooperative approach, where operators are responsible for coordinating and managing their own operations with the rules of the road, established under the regulatory and operational authority of the FAA [1]. ETM is particularly well-suited for higher airspace operations, as it offers a flexible and

scalable framework for managing diverse airspace users. With its emphasis on cooperative operations and distributed decision-making, ETM offers a more effective solution for accommodating the diverse range of HAPS.

As the demand for higher airspace operations continues to grow, it is imperative to adopt innovative approaches to airspace management [6]. The ETM concept provides a promising framework for ensuring the safe and efficient integration of diverse vehicles and missions in the UCE airspace [7]. By leveraging advanced technologies, promoting cooperative operations, and fostering industry-government partnerships, ETM can help realize the full potential of HAPS and other higher airspace operations [1].

II. UPPER CLASS E TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT (ETM)

At NASA Ames Research Center, ETM research efforts continue to mature under the National Airspace System (NAS) Exploratory Concepts and Technologies (NExCT) sub-project, which is a component of the Air Traffic Management – eXploration (ATM-X) project. In the envisioned ETM concept, a service-oriented ETM architecture, centered around an ETM Service Supplier (ESS), facilitates operation planning, intent sharing, strategic conflict detection, coordination, negotiation and resolution, as well as situational awareness [7]. The ESS exchanges information with ETM Clients, which are equipped with user interfaces (UIs) and transmit Operational Intent (OIs), updates, and telemetry data to the ESS. The ESS Network, composed of multiple ESSs, interfaces with Air Traffic Services (ATS) to ensure seamless integration with the broader air traffic management system (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Generalized ETM System

ETM operations occur within designated Cooperative Areas (CAs) authorized by the FAA. ETM vehicles must meet specific requirements to access a CA, including sharing location and intent data, and adhering to Cooperative Operating Practices (COPs). COPs are industry-defined agreements governing operator interactions within the ETM domain, empowering vehicle operators to coordinate, execute, and manage operations within FAA regulations [8].

Vehicles that fly within CAs must share their OIs via the ESS. OIs are four-dimensional (4D) representations of a vehicle's intended flight path. Accurate OI sharing is crucial for strategic conflict detection and resolution, with operators

responsible for adhering to their declared OIs. Sharing of OIs is an important mechanism for maintaining situational awareness among the operators.

A simple method based on OI intersections, defined as overlapping OI volumes has been proposed for early implementation of strategic conflict identification (see Figure 2). A *strategic conflict* here is defined as a conflict between vehicles' future OI volumes, in contrast to a *tactical conflict*, which is defined as a vehicle-to-vehicle conflict that needs to be resolved in a more immediate timeframe.

Strategic deconfliction of future OI volumes is expected to be the key mechanism in ETM for maintaining safe distances between vehicles, and it is a preferred method over tactical, vehicle-to-vehicle deconfliction methods. Strategic deconfliction is especially critical for vehicles with low maneuverability, or for vehicle pairs that vary widely in speed because in these situations, tactical resolutions may not provide enough time to maneuver or space to maintain safe separation distances.

Figure 2. Operational Intent (OI) volumes for a balloon and a fixed wing HALE with an OI intersection

As the operators periodically update their OIs, the ESS monitors and checks for OI intersections between all vehicle pairs and shares the overlapping OI volume information with the impacted operators. When an intersection is detected, the operators can engage in a negotiation process, guided by COPs, to resolve the conflicts. According to COPs, once a strategic conflict has been detected, operators are responsible for managing and resolving the detected conflicts. The detailed definitions of the COPs are yet to be determined, but they are expected to be rule-based, ad-hoc, or other methods that can guarantee vehicle safety and nominally provide a resolution of the conflict.

ETM development has been a collaborative effort involving the FAA, NASA, and industry partners since 2019. Regular NASA-led meetings and various virtual and in-person discussions have advanced the concept. Furthermore, a working session with industry stakeholders led to an initial set of COPs

for OI sharing and strategic conflict negotiation. Recent efforts have focused on identifying a flexible set of COPs that can accommodate diverse vehicle operations while providing sufficient structure for implementation.

These discussions and industry feedback have led to an initial ETM operational concept. To progress the concept development further, NASA initiated a real-time Collaborative Evaluation #1 (CE-1) simulation, with industry partners. CE-1 demonstrated the first instantiation of the ESS and ETM architecture that was used to test the scenarios and procedures envisioned for high altitude operations [9].

III. COLLABORATIVE EVALUATION STUDY

The ETM concept and intent sharing framework was developed and tested in the first collaborative evaluation with external partners, Aerostar and AeroVironment, who provided expertise on high-altitude balloons and slow, fixed wing HALEs, respectively. A simulation-based evaluation focusing on OI sharing and strategic conflict resolution was conducted at NASA Ames Research Center and the partners' remote sites in June 2024 (see Figure 3). For CE-1, NASA provided secure access to a prototype ESS via cloud-based services to these partners, who assumed the role of ETM operators for the strategic conflict detection, negotiation, and resolution procedures. Using their respective ETM Clients, the partners connected and exchanged data with the NASA ETM Service Supplier (NASA ESS) to participate in real-time evaluations. This demonstration showcased the information exchange foundational to the ETM concept, comparing cooperative traffic management to traditional methods for handling traffic in higher airspace operations.

Figure 3. Exchange of Operational Intent information between remotely located partners and NASA’s ESS

Aerostar and AeroVironment representatives were present on-site at NASA Ames to participate in CE-1, while their engineers assumed the role of vehicle operators to submit their OIs from remote locations. NASA engineers were also dispatched to these locations to provide support to the industry counterparts and observe the operations from the remote site operators’ perspectives. The participants from Aerostar and AeroVironment, both on-site and at remote locations, observed the OI submission and the strategic conflict resolution processes and provided valuable insights into vehicle performance considerations for cooperative traffic management.

Four scenarios were simulated, three of which are described in this paper. These scenarios illustrated step-by-step procedures

for OI submission, updates, strategic conflict detection, assessment, negotiation, and resolution, with varying levels of conflict, from no conflict to low-likelihood and high-likelihood conflicts that required negotiation. Scenario 1 presented the OI submissions and subsequent OI updates for vehicles with no conflicts. Scenario 2A had a low-likelihood conflict that was detected, but the operators negotiated to “wait-and-see” without making immediate changes to the vehicles’ trajectories. Scenario 2B had a high-likelihood conflict that needed to be resolved via negotiation by the operators and required a change in the vehicle’s trajectory. Figure 4 shows an illustration of the high-likelihood conflict detection and its resolution.

Figure 4. CE-1 Scenario 2B: Strategic Conflict Detection (top) and Resolution (bottom) with a High-Likelihood Conflict.

During each scenario, associated COPs were introduced, and feedback was elicited. For Scenario 1, which introduced how the operators would submit the initial OIs and subsequent updates in a non-conflict scenario, discussions were held with the on-site

operators at various points during the demonstration in real-time and they focused on COPs related to OI submission and updates. Scenario 2A introduced vehicles in strategic conflict to exercise procedures for strategic conflict detection, triggered by an OI intersection between a balloon and a slow HALE vehicle. The discussions focused on strategic conflict detection, acknowledgment, OI updates after the conflict, and the decision-making process for immediate or delayed resolution. Scenario 2B delved into strategic conflict negotiation, discussing strategies for resolving conflicts, and the steps involved in actively rerouting vehicles to eliminate a high-likelihood conflict.

These scenarios, along with the associated COPs, demonstrated in a step-by-step process how ETM vehicle operators can negotiate to resolve strategic conflicts. The information exchange between the NASA ESS and ETM vehicle operators was validated using the data collection capabilities of CE-1. At the beginning of each scenario, operators submitted Operation Plans and OI information. The scenarios played out in real time, with vehicles operating according to scripted position/telemetry data. The on-site industry partners observed the visualization of 4D Operational Volumes and trajectories on the NASA prototype ETM Client UI and discussed the process of using OI updates to resolve conflicts. These discussions, along with written post-run and post-study questionnaires, provided feedback on operational intent sharing and operator interactions during strategic conflict detection and resolution. A summary of the COPs results from the demonstration study are reported in the following section.

IV. FEEDBACK ON OI SHARING AND OPERATOR INTERACTIONS FROM THE CE-1 DEMONSTRATION

A. OI Submission and Updates

1) OI Characteristics

During the initial OI submission, partners provided feedback on the overall OI characteristics and parameters modeled for CE-1 that were implemented based on discussions with ETM industry operators during prior workshops and tabletop activities. The following is a summary of their feedback on the OI parameters that were modeled and discussed.

a) Conflict Management and Informational OIs

Early discussions with the ETM community revealed a desire to exchange operational and mission plans well in advance of the operation. However, concerns arose about the timing of strategic deconfliction happening too far in advance, resulting in potentially unnecessary maneuvers, particularly for vehicles with large, uncertain OI volumes, like balloons. To address this, NASA and FAA researchers proposed two types of OIs: Conflict Management and Informational.

Conflict Management OIs populate the near-term lookahead time horizon, ensuring high certainty, proactive updates and manageable volume sizes. Any strategic conflicts detected within this horizon must be negotiated and resolved. This “conflict negotiation / resolution time horizon” is called the Minimum Lookahead Time Window, and it must be populated

with Conflict Management OIs that have a Containment Confidence Level (CCL) of 95% or greater.

Informational OIs, on the other hand, provide situational awareness beyond the Minimum Lookahead Time Window. They may have larger, less certain volumes and less frequent updates compared to Conflict Management OIs. For these OI volumes, their sizes can be adjusted to be smaller by allowing them to have CCL values less than 95%. Figure 5 illustrates these two types of OIs.

Figure 5. Conflict Management and Informational OI volumes. Minimum Lookahead Time Window defines the lookahead time that requires conflict negotiation when a strategic conflict is detected. Conflict Management OIs require a CCL $\geq 95\%$

When these two OI types were presented to the partners in CE-1, they found the Conflict Management and Informational OI concepts both acceptable and feasible. These OI types worked well in CE-1 scenarios. Requiring strategic conflict negotiation within the Minimum Lookahead Time Window and basing the size of Conflict Management OIs on a CCL of 95% or greater seemed appropriate to the partners. Additionally, sharing Informational OIs for general situational awareness was well received by them.

b) Minimum Lookahead Time Window

In CE-1, we presented Conflict Management OI volumes with a 2-hour Minimum Lookahead Time Window. The partners suggested a Minimum Lookahead Time Window between 1–3 hours, with a preference for a shorter window for balloons and a longer window for slow-moving HALE vehicles. The consensus among the partners on the Minimum Lookahead Time Window was that it should depend on the vehicle’s performance characteristics. *Higher-performance vehicles*, which are less susceptible to wind and other atmospheric parameters such as air pressure/density, can provide more confident predictions and longer lookahead windows. In contrast, maintaining a high confidence level (e.g., 95% CCL) for a long duration may not be desirable for the *lower-performance vehicles*, which led to the discussion of dynamically adjusting the Time Window as a possibility.

Another key discussion point centered around scenarios where vehicles have different Minimum Lookahead Time Windows. For example, if two vehicles are both using the same 2-hour Minimum Lookahead Time Window, and a strategic conflict is detected 90 minutes into the future, they have a *negotiation window* of 90 minutes to resolve the conflict. However, if one vehicle has a shorter lookahead (e.g., 1 hour) and another has a longer window (e.g., 3 hours), a participant argued that the negotiation window should be based on the

shorter of the two timeframes (in this example, a maximum of 1 hour). This is because the vehicle with the shorter lookahead cannot reliably predict its position beyond their Lookahead Window, making any negotiation impractical because it would be based on uncertain information. This topic was further explored during the conflict negotiation scenarios, which will be reported in later sections.

c) *Containment Confidence Level (CCL)*

When asked about their ability to submit and conform to Conflict Management OIs with a 95% or greater CCL, the partners expressed confidence in meeting this target. While even higher CCLs (e.g., 99%) are possible, maintaining a lower CCL (i.e., closer to 95%), if feasible, would be beneficial, especially for balloons, as it would reduce the OI volume size, which in turn would reduce the number of conflict alerts and make conflict management more manageable. Although 95% CCL would imply that a vehicle may potentially be outside of its OI volume at 5% of the time, the participants felt that the operator should be able to mitigate this outcome by closely monitoring their vehicle’s trajectory predictions to check its conformance to the OI volumes and updating its OIs whenever its trajectory is predicted to be out of conformance.

d) *OI Volume Size*

The higher the CCL, the larger the volume size must be to ensure conformance. Prior to CE-1, the COPs for Conflict Management OIs were defined to allow the OIs to be greater than 95% CCL, which led to a concern that the operators could submit large OIs with higher CCL (e.g., 99%) that might occupy too much airspace volume and significantly impact other nearby vehicles. Therefore, we asked the partners whether there was sufficient incentive for the operators to keep the OI volumes as small as possible without additional COPs.

Their feedback suggested that there is a tradeoff between OI size and accuracy. Smaller OIs can improve airspace efficiency, but they require higher levels of precision and prediction accuracy. Larger OIs may allow vehicles to maintain high conformance with less precision, which can in turn provide more flexibility, especially for vehicles with uncertain trajectories.

However, occupying larger OI volumes can also increase the likelihood of conflicts alerts, which could increase the number of unnecessary negotiations for vehicle pairs that would not result in vehicle-to-vehicle conflicts. Ultimately, the optimal OI size and update frequency will depend on various factors, including vehicle capabilities, operational requirements, and the specific airspace environment.

2) *Initial OI Submission*

a) *Acceptability and Feasibility of the OI Submission*

At the beginning of each scenario, the partners submitted OIs from their respective remote sites to the NASA ESS, which shared the information with the other vehicles participating in the simulation. During Scenario 1, the partners discussed the initial OI submission process, which they thought was very acceptable and feasible

Table 1 shows the questionnaire feedback provided by the three partners that participated in-person at NASA Ames. They

commented that to ensure effective conflict detection, COPs should mandate that all operators submit their OIs to an ESS so that it can share their OI information with other operators, and when a strategic conflict (i.e., overlapping OI volumes) is detected, OI updates should be submitted more frequently. While the process of submitting and modifying conflicting OIs is acceptable, the participants commented that the process of submitting frequent updates may become cumbersome if it must be repeated frequently.

TABLE I. CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND INFORMATIONAL OI VOLUMES. QUESTIONNAIRE RESPONSES WERE BASED ON 5-POINT RATING SCALES

Based on your vehicle type, how feasible is it to build the OI volumes ?	Very Feasible (3)
Do you agree with the notion of using both “Conflict Management” and “Informational” OIs?	Yes, Agree (3)
How easy/difficult would it be to develop a single submission that encompasses both “Conflict Management” and “Informational” OIs?	Somewhat Easy (1)
	Very Easy (2)
Rate how likely/unlikely it is that you would be able to create and share Operational Intent for:	
Transitioning as part of a Mission	Very Likely (3)
Loitering as part of a Mission	Very Likely (3)
The COPs were feasible for:	
“Conflict Management” OI Volumes ($\geq 95\%$ CCL)	Very Feasible (3)
“Informational” OI Volumes	Very Feasible (3)

3) *OI Updates – When No Conflicts Are Detected*

For Conflict Management OIs, when no conflict is detected, *approximate* update rates of every 30 minutes were recommended by the partners, and for Informational OIs, a 24-hour update cycle was reasonable, especially for less-dynamic operations. In general, there should be a balance between accuracy with practicality. Given that the OI information might be old and no longer accurate near the end of the 24-hour cycle, a more practical update rate may be every 12 hours with 24-hour lookahead window. Overall, the goal should be to strike a balance between providing sufficient information for safe operations while minimizing the burden to the operators.

Participant feedback emphasized the importance of frequent OI updates to maintain conformance with their published OI volumes. They suggested that frequent updates could help to maintain situational awareness for other operators. There was a strong preference for automating the OI updates, which could facilitate the frequent updates without increased workload.

When updating OIs, operators must maintain accuracy and compliance. If a vehicle goes out of conformance, the operator is responsible for taking immediate action, whether it is updating the OI to reflect the current position or resolving the conflict

with other operators. Ensuring that operators consistently provide accurate and timely updates is essential.

Operators who frequently deviate from their declared OIs can erode trust within the system. The operators should also avoid creating a new conflict with another operator’s OIs when they update their own OIs. The ESS should play an active role in monitoring operator behavior and taking appropriate actions, such as issuing warnings or alerts, to maintain system integrity.

B. Conflict Detection and Subsequent OI Update

In Scenario 2A of CE-1, the partners stepped through the process of strategic conflict detection, initial coordination between the operators, submitting OI updates in response to the conflict, and conflict assessment and decision making.

1) Conflict Detection and Acknowledgment

In CE-1, the NASA ESS monitored for strategic conflicts and alerted the impacted operators. However, there was no capability for operators to explicitly acknowledge receipt of the conflict alerts to the ESS or other impacted operators. The consensus from the partners was that a more explicit acknowledgement capability should be integrated into the coordination process. Figure 6 provides an example of such an acknowledgement. A mechanism for operators to acknowledge conflicts could be implemented as a simple button/notification in the ETM Client UI. This acknowledgement confirms that an operator is aware of the conflict and is taking appropriate action to resolve it.

Figure 6. An example of the operator’s ETM Client UI: “Acknowledge Conflict” button can send the acknowledgement message to the ESS to share with other impacted parties.

To facilitate conflict resolution, it is essential to provide operators with sufficient information about the conflict. This includes details such as the identity of the conflicting vehicles, their altitudes, speeds, headings, and the nature of the conflict. A clear and concise visualization of the conflict can help operators quickly assess the situation and develop appropriate response strategies. Partners also preferred all operators to use a common information exchange system and adhere to standardized data formats to maintain consistency and accuracy

of the information to enable seamless information exchange and facilitate automated conflict detection and resolution.

The accuracy of wind data was also considered critical in predicting vehicle trajectories and avoiding conflicts. To improve the accuracy of wind forecasts, it may be beneficial for the ESS or another third-party service to aggregate and distribute wind data from multiple sources. This could involve purchasing wind data from different providers and then reselling it to operators at a reduced cost.

2) OI Update in Response to the Conflict

The COPs for Strategic Deconfliction specified that the first step upon receiving a conflict alert is to update their Conflict Management OIs (i.e., those OI volumes that fall within the Minimum Lookahead Time Window). The partners agreed with the proposed COPs for OI updates in CE-1, which outlined that the operators should update their OIs as soon as they detect the conflict and strive to reduce their OI volume size while maintaining a CCL of 95% or greater. Using smaller OI volumes, which can be achieved while meeting the required CCL as defined in the COPs, may reduce conflict alerts, simplify conflict resolution, and improve airspace efficiency.

When a conflict is detected for controllable balloons, they suggested to reduce the OI volume size, shrink the Minimum Lookahead Time Window, and increase the update rate. Figure 7 illustrates the suggestion made during CE-1 to reduce the overall OI volume size by decreasing volume duration from 30 to 10 minutes, shrinking the Minimum Lookahead Time Window from 1 hour to 30 minutes, and increasing the update rate from every 30 minutes to every 1–2 minutes.

Figure 7. An example of a balloon’s OI size, Minimum Lookahead Time Window, and update rate changes before and after the strategic conflict detection.

The operator of the slow fixed-wing HALEs also wanted to increase the update rate to every 1–2 minutes but preferred to maintain the same OI volume size (e.g., 30-minute duration) and Minimum Lookahead Time Window (e.g., 2–3 hours) as their *initial* OI submission, prior to a conflict being detected. Once a strategic conflict is detected, the partners emphasized the importance of frequent OI updates for maintaining accurate situational awareness and the need to resolve the conflict promptly. However, the update frequency should be tailored to the specific vehicle's capabilities and the complexity of the operating environment. Slower-moving vehicles, like balloons, may require less frequent updates, while faster vehicles may need more frequent updates.

A balance between precision and flexibility is necessary in determining OI volume size. While a more precise (i.e., smaller) OI volumes can improve conflict avoidance, they may also limit operational flexibility. A flexible and adaptive approach to OI management is essential. By carefully considering factors such as vehicle type, operational requirements, and airspace complexity, operators can optimize their OI strategies to ensure safe and efficient operations.

There was a strong consensus on automating the OI update process, although human judgment and intervention may still be necessary for complex situations. Clear guidelines for OI submission, update rate, and conflict resolution are essential to ensure consistency and predictability.

C. Conflict Assessment

The conflict assessment process begins with an initial coordination between the operators of the conflicting vehicles. The initial contact should occur as soon as possible after the alert is received to establish a common understanding of the conflict.

1) Communication and Coordination

Discussions with the partners highlighted the importance of effective communication and coordination in resolving conflicts. While direct communication between operators is sufficient for low-density scenarios, it would become challenging and time-consuming as traffic density increases. One approach to mitigate this issue is to reduce the size of OI volumes and shorten the lookahead time. This would simplify the coordination process by reducing the number of potential strategic conflicts. Also, by anticipating potential conflicts, operators could adjust their flight plans and OI volumes to avoid or minimize conflicts. For example, if the traffic patterns indicate that a specific airspace will be congested, operators could choose alternative routes or altitudes to reduce the likelihood of conflicts.

When a conflict is detected, operators should be prepared to communicate with each other to coordinate their actions. This may involve adjusting their flight paths, speeds, or altitudes to avoid the conflict. Clear and concise communication is essential to ensure that all parties understand the situation and agree on a course of action. The partners highlighted the need for robust digital communication channels, in addition to voice channels, for ETM operations. While traditional voice communication remains essential for immediate coordination, digital communication tools can provide additional benefits. A

persistent digital communication history can serve as a valuable record of agreements and decisions made during the coordination process.

Some of the commonly occurring messages during strategic conflict negotiation, such as “conflict alert received,” “currently assessing resolution options,” “waiting for the next update cycle,” could be coded into predefined messages or alerts, that may be exchanged via the ESS or by direct connection between the operators. A shared digital platform, such as a chat room, could also facilitate asynchronous communication, allowing operators to exchange information and coordinate plans without relying on real-time voice communication. This may help to reduce clutter on voice channels and improve overall communication efficiency. These types of digital platforms would be established as a direct connection between the operators, outside of ESS framework.

2) Minimum Lookahead Time Window and OI Volume Size

When examining whether the Minimum Lookahead Time Window should be modified in response to a conflict, the balloon and slow fixed wing HALE vehicle types had different responses for ideal time horizons (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. OI size and Minimum Lookahead Time Windows for the balloon and slow HALE OIs: after the strategic conflict detection

For balloons, a shorter time horizon (e.g., 30 minutes or less) was more beneficial, and the partner also emphasized the need for shorter temporal duration for each OI volume. While a 30-minute update rate might suffice for non-conflict situations, finer-grained updates will be necessary for safe and efficient operations. Specifically, the need for more frequent update rates, along with smaller OI sizes and shorter temporal durations, at intervals of every 20 minutes, 10 minutes, and even 5 minutes within the Minimum Lookahead Time Window. This increased resolution is crucial for accurately representing the balloon's trajectory and enabling timely conflict detection and resolution,

especially during critical phases of flight where uncertainties are higher. In contrast, the slow fixed wing HALE operator also expressed the need for more frequent update rates but would keep the longer time horizon and the temporal size of the OI volume (e.g., 30 minutes).

3) Conflict Likelihood Calculator

During the conflict assessment, the partners expressed a desire for a conflict likelihood metric to prioritize which conflicts to resolve immediately versus which to monitor (wait-and-see). They suggested that this metric be calculated based on the overlap between OI volumes and their temporal evolution, meaning that as the time of potential conflict approaches, the likelihood of conflict should ideally increase. If the overlapping area of the OIs is expanding and the likelihood is increasing, as the conflict nears, it would suggest that the conflict may not resolve itself and requires operator intervention. Such a metric would be valuable for operator decision making. If the likelihood of conflict remains high despite operator actions, it indicates that the chosen resolution strategy may be ineffective. This feedback could prompt operators to explore alternative solutions.

Ideally, a conflict likelihood metric could be used to automate the prioritization of conflicts, within the limits of an established set of COPs for the strategic conflicts. The system could prioritize conflicts with a high and increasing likelihood of occurrence for immediate operator attention and focus their attention on the most critical conflicts.

4) Decision to Resolve vs. Wait-and-See

Upon detection and evaluation of a conflict, the operator must determine whether to initiate immediate resolution or to adopt a wait-and-see strategy. Whichever course of action is selected, it is imperative to coordinate with other affected operators to develop a collective understanding of the anticipated resolution. The subsequent sections on negotiation and resolution elaborate on the methods employed to achieve this coordination.

While the idea of allowing conflicts to resolve naturally by waiting for OI volumes to shrink is appealing, it carries the potential for undesirable consequences. This strategy could encourage operators to rely excessively on passive resolution, potentially neglecting proactive measures to avoid conflicts.

Moreover, this approach might incentivize operators to take fewer proactive steps to deconflict. While controllable balloons may have greater flexibility to maneuver within an hour (versus a slow-HALE vehicle which may require more planning/inputs before executing a maneuver), relying solely on passive resolution within this timeframe could be risky. Partners from the slow-HALE side commented that conflicts not actively managed within the first hour may become more difficult and time-consuming to resolve.

In contrast, the partner from the controllable balloon side commented that waiting to resolve the conflict has a large benefit. For balloons, OI volume size is expected to shrink significantly within the last 10–30 minutes (because the accuracy of their near-term (10–30 minutes) trajectory prediction is much higher), so the conflict-related deviation

could be minimized with less impact on their overall mission. For the controllable balloons, *vertical* maneuvers can be executed over short time frames while maintaining safety.

In addition, there were concerns about the limitations of long-term planning and early conflict resolutions for balloons. Pre-programmed flight paths can limit flexibility and adaptability in response to unforeseen circumstances. For example, if a thunderstorm develops, the operator might need to deviate from the pre-programmed plan to avoid the storm. Long-term planning can restrict such flexibility, potentially leading to suboptimal or even unsafe flight trajectories.

All parties agreed that when a strategic conflict is detected, there is a need for a more frequent OI updates to enable operators to make more informed decisions and take proactive measures to avoid the conflict. By reducing the update intervals within the first hour, operators can gain a better understanding of the evolving situation and take appropriate action to deconflict. This proactive approach is crucial for ensuring safety and efficiency in ETM operations.

D. Conflict Negotiation and Resolution

1) Negotiation Procedures

In CE-1, ad-hoc negotiation procedures were used, in which the operators negotiated with each other upon detecting a strategic conflict to devise potential resolution options. Feedback from the partners showed that these procedures were generally acceptable, assuming that there would be human operators / pilots who are available on-demand to assess the situation and negotiate the solutions in low-density operations.

A concern was raised that the ad-hoc negotiation process could be cumbersome and time-consuming if it required submitting and revising multiple resolution plan options until one is accepted. Automated tools may be useful to manage conflicts, prioritizing those that pose the greatest risk and require immediate attention. This would allow operators to focus their efforts on the most critical situations, improving efficiency and reducing the burden of manual coordination.

Additionally, they emphasized the importance of timely conflict resolution. Relying on a wait-and-see approach could be ineffective and may lead to delays in addressing critical issues. Effective communication and coordination between operators are also crucial for successful resolution of strategic conflicts

A suggestion was made to implement a "deconflict" button in the UI that would send a message to the other operators. When a strategic conflict is detected, pressing this button could automatically open a chat window with the other operator involved in the conflict, facilitating direct communication and coordination between the operators to resolve the conflict. Following the resolution, one/both operators would update their near-term OI to reflect the agreed-upon solution.

Finally, for scaled, high-density, and more automated operations under m:N conditions (m:N, where **m** represents the number of operators and **N** represents the number of vehicles per **m** operators), ad-hoc negotiation would need to be replaced by a more structured or automated process for the concept

feasibility. As the number of interactions increases, the need for automated tools becomes crucial.

Structured and automated negotiation process is being researched in parallel to the concept development and evaluation process described in this paper. Game-theory based negotiation algorithm has been proposed, developed, and evaluated for two-party conflict negotiation [10]. The results suggest that such algorithms can provide successful negotiation process that is flexible, transparent, and automated conflict resolutions that may be more efficient in total than non-negotiated solutions [10]. Subsequently, the method has been expanded for multi-party negotiation and is currently being evaluated [11].

2) Negotiation Strategies

During the discussions about how the operators might negotiate to resolve a strategic conflict, the partners brainstormed several different strategies. The following are some of the examples:

- Early Conflict Detection and Proactive Resolution:** Some vehicles (e.g., slow HALEs) may want to resolve the conflict *as early as possible*. Feedback indicated that operators should strive to identify and address potential conflicts well in advance, rather than waiting for the conflict to become closer in time/distance or for the likelihood of the conflict to increase. This proactive approach involves frequent updates to OIs and continuous monitoring of airspace.
- Flexible Maneuvering:** Other vehicles (e.g., balloons) may want to resolve the conflict *as late as safely possible*. Feedback was that operators should maintain flexibility in their flight plans so that they have the option to take action to resolve a strategic conflict, if needed. This might involve adjusting altitude, speed, or heading to avoid a conflict. The ability to quickly adapt to changing situations is essential, especially for balloons and other vehicles with limited maneuverability.
- Minimizing OI Volumes with Tighter Control:** Reducing the size of OI volumes and/or OI temporal resolution can significantly reduce the likelihood of conflicts. OI volumes could potentially be made smaller by maintaining a tighter control of the vehicles to reduce the temporal resolution of each volume and/or reduce the volume's altitude shelves (i.e., the height of the volume) in the near-term time horizon when a strategic conflict is detected. For example, two vehicle operators with overlapping OI volumes could each decide to hold more "tightly" (i.e., submit smaller OI volumes and hold operation within), holding at different altitudes from each other near the OI intersection as a method of resolving the conflict.

During CE-1 discussions, a two-step negotiation process emerged as a preferred solution. When a conflict is detected, the initial step should be to coordinate with the other operator to discuss potential resolution options. This initial communication allows for a shared understanding of the situation and enables

operators to explore various strategies for deconfliction. Once a preliminary understanding is reached, operators can monitor the situation and determine whether further action is necessary. This approach allows for flexibility and avoids unnecessary maneuvers if the conflict resolves naturally, through regularly scheduled OI updates.

Figure 9 illustrates a potential mapping of this two-step negotiation process to the two different Minimum Lookahead Time Window durations discussed earlier. In this scenario, two vehicles have 1- and 3-hour Minimum Lookahead Time Windows, respectively. In Figure 9, the two operators could begin the negotiation process at the *initial contact point* at the longer of the two Minimum Lookahead Time Windows and begin to *discuss their resolution options* in the abstract and monitor the conflict situation. No strategic conflict negotiation is engaged until the conflict reaches the Minimum Lookahead Time Window for both vehicles. Once that point is reached, the conflict negotiation process begins in earnest within the *active negotiation window*, in which the conflict could be resolved using one of the earlier discussed resolution options discussed earlier, or new ones if the updated vehicle information changes their resolution strategies.

Figure 9. Illustration of the two-step negotiation process

3) Resolution Strategies

The discussion with the on-site partners frequently centered on the limitations of maneuverability for some vehicles, such as balloons. Altitude control is often the most effective and discrete means of maneuvering for the controllable balloons, which can be done most efficiently with minimal deviation if done as late as safely possible. Different vehicle characteristics highlight the need for flexible and adaptable conflict resolution strategies that consider the unique characteristics and limitations of different aircraft types.

The need for flexible resolution strategies was emphasized throughout CE-1. For example, deconfliction strategies may vary depending on the time of day/night. Because balloons may descend and hold a lower altitude during nighttime operations, they may be more likely to resolve a conflict at night by

maintaining a *lower* altitude; while during the day, maintaining a *higher* altitude may be the resolution strategy that is most suitable for their operation.

Partners also emphasized the importance of minimizing the need for complex maneuvers to resolve conflicts. They suggested that simple adjustments, such as limiting the base altitude of a balloon to avoid conflict with another aircraft, could be more effective and less disruptive to overall mission goals.

The inherent uncertainty in predicting vehicle trajectories, particularly due to factors like wind variations, was also acknowledged. This uncertainty can significantly complicate conflict resolution efforts. Finally, the topic of standardization was mentioned multiple times during CE-1. The feedback suggested a need for standardized procedures for conflict resolution.

4) *Equity and Trust*

Discussions on conflict resolution raised concerns about equity and trust among operators. One participant noted that operators who consistently accommodate conflicts by altering their own OI / flight plan might be at a disadvantage. To address this, the suggestion was made to establish mechanisms within the COPs to ensure equitable burden sharing, perhaps by rotating who takes the initiative to adjust during conflict resolution.

Furthermore, several discussions highlighted the critical role of *trust* in the success of the ETM system. The feasibility of ETM hinges on the operators' compliance with the agreed-upon COPs and negotiation outcomes. This includes maintaining conformance with declared OIs, responding promptly to conflict resolutions, and maintaining safe separation distances between vehicles.

Regulations alone cannot effectively address situations where operators consistently fail to adhere to these agreements, especially when some conflicts may be resolved by simply reducing the size of OI volumes by a small amount to avoid overlapping volumes. Ensuring effective vehicle control within declared OI volumes, which assumes accurate wind and vehicle modeling, is paramount. To address non-compliant behavior, the establishment of procedures and rules with appropriate incentives and reprimands for vehicles/operators that do not adhere to COPs is necessary.

V. CONCLUSION

CE-1 demonstrated the feasibility of collaborative traffic management in the Upper Class E airspace in a simulated environment, realizing the first instantiation of the ESS and the ETM architecture. The industry partners actively participated in the evaluation, successfully connecting to the NASA ESS by submitting and updating OIs and their positions from remote locations and implementing OI revisions to resolve strategic conflicts caused by overlapping OI volumes.

The partners were actively engaged throughout the process and provided valuable feedback on the OI submission and negotiation processes. Visualizing operations and role playing these processes from the operator's perspective allowed them to provide valuable insights into how OI sharing and operator interactions should be conducted for strategic deconfliction. The

concept of having distinct Conflict Management OIs and Informational OIs was deemed acceptable and helpful. Strategic conflict negotiation was determined to be mandatory only within the context of Conflict Management OIs, which were recommended to have a short lookahead time horizon. To further reduce the likelihood of conflicts and the subsequent maneuvers for deconfliction, it was suggested that the temporal resolution for the OI volumes in the Conflict Management OIs should be short (e.g., 10 minutes for balloons).

For the strategic conflict detection, negotiation, and resolution process, the evaluation highlighted the need for a digital communication channel to facilitate conflict acknowledgment, operator-to-operator chat, and other communication needs. It was also recognized that a two-step negotiation process might be necessary. This would involve an initial discussion between operators to explore potential resolution solutions early on, followed by a period of observation to determine if the conflict resolves itself before taking any action. The development of a conflict likelihood calculator that displays both the likelihood value and the trends of that value was deemed beneficial for informed decision making. The evaluation emphasized the importance of trust in the other party's ability to conform to their OI volumes, which requires accurate wind and vehicle modeling and appropriate responses to conflict situations.

CE-1 demonstration provided a better understanding of the end-user requirements for the ETM system and obtained valuable operational test data to verify service efficiency and accuracy. The partners benefited by having their operational needs and constraints reflected in the development of the ETM concept, potentially expediting the implementation of ETM in the NAS for improved access to Upper Class E airspace. To continue advancing the ETM concept, future collaborative evaluations can integrate more COPs and involve more industry partners/vehicles in future collaborative evaluations.

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